

Perceived usefulness - (PU)

U1. Using the designed interface would enable me to accomplish tasks more quickly.

U2. Using the designed interface would improve my performance.

U3. Using the designed interface would increase my productivity.

U4. Using the designed interface would increase my effectiveness.

U5. Using the designed interface would make it easier to do my job.

U6. I would find the designed interface useful.

Perceived ease of use - (PEOU)

E1. Learning to operate the designed interface would be easy for me.

E2. I would find it easy to get the designed interface to do what I want it to do, to mediate the actions of other bots and present it on the pull request.

E3. My interaction with the designed interface would be clear and understandable.

E4. It would be easy for me to become skillful at using the designed interface.

E5. It is easy to remember how to perform tasks using the designed interface.

E6. I would find the designed interface easy to use.

Self-prediction of Future Use (SPFU)

S1. Assuming the designed interface would be available, I predict that I will use it in the future.

S2. I would prefer using the designed interface to the existing interface.